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THE COMPARISON OF WORDS IN THE TRANSLATION IS IN THE
EXAMPLE OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses about the comparative change of words in the process of translating from English to Uzbek and from Uzbek to English, and discusses some given examples.

Keywords: Translation, linguistics, comparative analysis, compound words, lexical words, word form .

Today, in our country, special attention is paid to learning foreign languages, especially English. Several decrees and decisions on the development of foreign languages are being adopted by the head of state and our government. This means how important it is to learn foreign languages.

The art of translation and reproduction is a high-art creation, even if it is a creation, it is a creation that requires dedication, work, patience, and painstaking work on various materials. The meaning of the concept of translation is very broad, because "What is translation?" Representatives of different fields give different answers to this question. One person says that translation is the translation of a book written in one language into another language, while another person considers it to be the explanation of an idea expressed in one language to people who speak another language. According to a third person, movies are also translated, so translation means translating the speech of an actor playing a role in one language into a second, third, and so on. From the point of view of linguistic translation, translation can be defined as follows:

Translation, which is a complex form of human activity, is a creative process of re-creating a speech expression (text) created in one language, preserving its unity of form and content, based on the means of another language. So, the speech expression created using the means of the original language is replaced by such an expression created on the basis of the laws of the translated language. In these 8 ways, the substantive and stylistic adequacy of the texts of the original and translation languages is created. Translation is a powerful tool that serves the interests of friendship, brotherhood and cooperation between peoples, and the expansion of economic, political, scientific, cultural and literary relations between them. All the above comments about translation have a soul. Because each of them describes the translation

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from one side and serves to complete the general understanding of it. So, translation is a multi-faceted, fast-paced, complex activity. Translation is one of the most ancient types of human activity, thanks to which we clearly imagine the history of human development in all its details. Translation accelerates the process of interaction and influence of literature of different nations. Thanks to translated works, readers enjoy the masterpieces of world literature, their aesthetic feelings increase, their tastes grow, and they develop concepts about beautiful things. Translation, as a necessary tool for the development of languages, accelerates the pace of their development, increases and improves vocabulary. Translation enriches a person's spiritual life and expands the possibilities of the mother tongue.

The achievements of comparative linguistics are effectively used in the translation. The purpose of comparative analysis in translation is to study general rules in the translation process. Comparative analysis in translation theory is based on the facts (evidence) accepted as the result of comparative analysis of words and sentences. A comparative study of the different characteristics of words in English and words in other languages shows that there are different characteristics of words in English and other languages. The word form, the semantic structure of related words and the use of ulam in speech are different in different languages. Each language has its own lexical structure. But not in all meanings, that is, you can find a word in Uzbek that expresses the meaning of the word in English. For example, compare the meanings of the word "hand" with the word "кол" that expresses its meaning. In addition, in English and Uzbek, related words form various artificial words. For example: "hand" (handful, handiness), "kol" (kolla, kolsez kol, kolly). in so many ways they are not compatible with each other. For example: To take an exam; To take tea; To take off-jechinm white; to give an examination; to have a rest; to photograph. The semantic structure of a word in the Uzbek language may have a specific formal meaning that is not present in the English word expressing the meaning of the word.

For example: This event was a good lesson to me. The level of lexical valence of an English word is not the same as that of an Uzbek word. For example: the Uzbek word "kotarma" can be combined with nouns such as "kol" and "chair". But the English verb "to raise" expressing its meaning can only be combined with the noun "hand" ("to raise hands", but not "to raise chair", but "to lift chair"). Several synonyms of the same type in English can be translated by one word in Uzbek. For example: the verbs "accept, admit, adopt, take, receive" represent the word "accept". The word "artist" in Uzbek is represented by three different words in English. They are "painter, artist, drawer". The word "Blow" is translated into six words in Uzbek (hit, hit, hit, hit, knock, kick). More than 20 words in the English language express the concept of "hit". They say "blow; smack slap; whack; poke dig; rap; knock stroke" and h. Some languages are rich in

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words with significant special meanings, while others express general concepts and reject secondary meaning. French is generally considered to be a very abstract language, while German is a language that is concrete and full of specific concepts. In German, there are three special verbs that express the same general concept in French, French uses artificial words in most cases, and German and English use more compound words: cendrier-ashtray, aschenbecher; theriere-tea pot... A comparative study of the structure of the English and Uzbek languages shows that a number of simple, artificial and compound words can be almost corrected to each other. But when we translate English words into Uzbek, we see some differences, simple words are used more than artificial or compound words in English. The Uzbek language is rich in artificial and compound words, which are often used in speech, unlike the English language. Here are some sentences in English and Uzbek as examples. For example: pocket (pock), hamlet (ham), "Pock", "ham" morphemes are single (bo Min mas) morphemes, because they do not have meaning.

Words are the basis of all languages in the world. Also, people's speech depends on the use of these words. It is no exaggeration to say that it depends on having a large vocabulary and using synonyms in order for our speech to be fluent and not to repeat our words.

At this point, I would like to touch on one more point, the above synonymous situations can also be found in the structure of sentences. As in all languages, in English and Uzbek, the idea is conveyed to the listener in several ways. When we compare them as follows, I loved the girl; the girl I loved These examples are clear examples of syntactic synonymy. By using such synonyms in our speech, we can avoid various repetitions, the same and boring sentences, make the speech more attractive, unrepeatable, stylistically diverse and perform the unique function of the literary language. When communicating in Uzbek, English and similar languages, increasing the weight of synonyms used in them directly contributes to the stability of our speech and a high level of colorfulness. In conclusion, we are sure that every research conducted in linguistics will affect not only the enrichment of the Uzbek literary language, but also the spirituality of the people who speak this language. Studying such topics and ideas in harmony with English and other foreign languages serves as a foundation for every researcher and student, and is of great importance in further improving and polishing the studied object.

In conclusion, translation is a powerful tool that serves the interests of friendship, brotherhood and cooperation between peoples, and the expansion of economic, political, scientific, cultural and literary relations between them.

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REFERENCES

1. Translation Theory 2012, I. Gafurov
2. Peculiarities of translation pragmatics. 2014, Khudoiberdiyeva Ogiloy
3. Translation theory as a science 2017, Muhammadjon Holbekov
4. Islamova, M. Sh. "Fundamentals of Forming a Professional Worldview." Science and Education 2.Special Issue 1 (2021): 78-87.
5. Usarov, J. E., G. N. Sharipova, and Sh. S. Abdusamatova. "The role of student self-development competence in the effectiveness of education and its importance in practice." Science and Education 2.Special Issue 1 (2021): 276-285.
6. Usarov, J. E., L. G. Boboxodjaeva, and N. Yusupova. "The mixed form of education as a modern approach to the pedagogical education cluster." Science and Education 2.Special Issue 1 (2021): 286-295
7. Yuldashev, O. A. "Pedagogical Conditions for the Use of Man-Made Civilization in the Elementary Grades." Science and Education 2.Special Issue 1 (2021): 88-97.
8. Смиринцкий А.И. Синтаксис английского языка. –М., 1957
9. TursunovU., MuxtorovJ. Hozirgio'zbekadabiytili. –T., 1975

